

THE USE OF REAL ANTHROPONYMS IN FAIRY TALES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the use of names of real historical figures in fiction, especially in Uzbek and English fairy tales.

Key words: historical, real, character, artistic image, fairy tale, narrative, folklore, personality, anthroponym.

Introduction

All types of literary texts, including fairy tales, use real historical names. Such names create the impression that the events really happened and help ensure the vitality and believability of the fairy tale.

The main part

The name chosen for the character is one of the means of creating an artistic image, it describes the character's social affiliation, expresses national and local feeling, recreates historical reality if the action took place in the past (or if the name refers to reality (can destroy it if a conflict is selected) [5, 234].

In the fairy tale "Doro and Iskandarbek" Doro is a king, and Iskandarbek is his son, a king.

Bir vaqtda Doro degan katta podsho o'tgan ekan.

O'g'li – O'g'lining otini Iskandarbek qo'yibdi (At one time, a great king named Doro passed by. His son was named Iskandarbek) ("Doro va Iskandarbek").

Doro - Darius I was the great king of Persia, who lived and ruled from 522 to 486 BC. During his reign, Darius united and expanded the Persian Empire, and therefore remained in history as one of the greatest kings of the Persian people.

The anthroponym of Alexander is also considered a common image in the peoples of the East, this name is often found in fairy tales, narratives, and folklore texts.

Alexander the Great is a common character in the literature of the peoples of the East. This image is directly related to the activity of Alexander the Great. Alexander is widely known among the Muslim nations of the East under the name of Zulqarnain through the legends of the 18th chapter of the Qur'an. Alexander ascended the throne at the age of 20. In the East, they classified it as having a horn. After Alexander's father, Philip II, was assassinated, he ascended the throne. Alexander the Great was born in 356 BC. At that time, Alexander was brought up by the famous philosopher Aristotle. Alexander sat on the throne of Macedonia in 336 BC [6].

Historically, Darius and Alexander are not really father and son, but in the fairy tale, father and son came in the form of kings.

Alisher Navoi, Husayn Boygaro anthroponyms are also found in folktales typical of the Uzbek people. In particular, the anthroponym of Alisher Navoi as a famous poet and minister was the basis for the formation of a number of fairy tales. "Navoiy bilan mardikor" ("The laborer with Navai"), "Navoiy bilan cho'pon" ("The shepherd with Navai"), "Navoiy bilan yamoqchining o'g'li" "The son of the farmer with Navai", "Navoiy kimni yomon ko'rgan?" ("Who did Navai hate?") such tales are among them.

"In the narratives, there are real characters, and in fairy tales, fictional characters. However, some narrations were influenced by fairy tales and changed in their content. The exaggeration of Alisher Navoi's character in the narrative, in particular, his idealization, has already brought him close to the hero of a household fairy tale. At this point, it should be said that the storyteller did not describe the historical person as such, but on the contrary, brought him closer to an artistic image, in particular, when he idealized his wonderful qualities and imposed additional meanings, the real signs of the image, events and events became blurred, as a result, Alisher Navoi appeared not as a historical person in the narrative, but as a hero in a fairy tale. At the same time, the events and events that took place at a specific time are also transferred to the indefinite tense, the name of the person and place is preserved or omitted in the interpretation. Such a phenomenon applies to the approach of narratives to household tales" [4, 153-154].

There are also tales about both Alisher Navoi and Husayn Boykara. The fairy tales "Dunyoda nima lazzatli?" ("What is delicious in the world?"), "Navoiy va Husayn" ("Navai and Husayn") are examples of this.

Husayn Boykara (Husayni) (1438, Herat - May 4, 1506, Baba-Ilohi, near Herat) - a representative of the Timurid dynasty, the king of Khurasan, a famous Turkish poet and statesman.

It is a historical fact that Alisher Navoi and Husayn Boykara grew up together as contemporary friends from childhood, and later, when Husayn Boykara ascended the throne, Alisher Navoi became his minister. So, this truth is also reflected in fairy tales. In the fairy tale "Ziyad Batir" we meet the characters of Alisher Navoi and Sultan Husayn:

Ular ov qila-qila bir necha kun deganda bir shaharga boribdilar. Bu shaharning nomi Hirot ekan. Ana shu yerda Sulton Husayn mirzo podsho ekan.

Temirchi o'ylab-o'ylab:

-Bir yo'l bor, -debdi, -u ham bo'lsa podshoning vaziri Alisher Navoiy bilan uchrashasan, butun sirni unga aytasan, dardingga o'sha kishi davo topa oladi

After hunting, they went to a town for a few days. The name of this city is Herat. This is where Sultan Husayn Mirza is the king.

The blacksmith pondered:

"There is one way," he said, "and if there is one, you can meet Alisher Navoi, the king's minister, tell him the whole secret, and he can find a cure for your pain." ("Ziyod botir").

Abu Ali ibn Sina was famous as a scientist and physician both in the East and in the West. The anthroponym Abu Ali ibn Sina is also found in many fairy tales. Tales such as "The ignorant king and Abu Ali", "The chemist", "Ibn Sina and the madman", "Ibn Sina and education" appeared based on the name and life of Ibn Sina.

There are many real people in English fairy tales. King Arthur, knight of the round table is one of the most common anthroponyms.

King Arthur is the legendary king of England, the main hero of medieval literature. As a post-Roman Briton, Arthur is a king who fought against the Angles and Sconians in the 5th and 6th centuries. Geoffrey of Monmouth's 12th-century *Historia Regum Britanniae* portrays King Arthur as an invincible warrior, a ruler who fought the English and created a vast empire.

Also, in English fairy tales, we find the real anthroponyms of King Edward III, King Henry V.

King Edward III - lived in 1312-1377, was the King of England and Lord of Ireland from 1327 until the end of his life. Edward III restores the royal authority that his father Edward II destroyed, making England the most powerful military kingdom in Europe.

King Henry V - lived in 1386-1422, was the king of England from 1413 to the end of his life. During the reign of Henry V, the royal armed forces were greatly developed and won the Hundred Years' War against France. For this reason, Henry V is recognized as the most powerful warrior king of medieval England.

"Wittington and his cat" is a fairy tale based on real historical events, it is a fairy tale that illuminates the life of a poor boy until he becomes the mayor of London.

Dick Whittington is considered a real person. Therefore, the anthroponyms in the fairy tale are also considered to be historical figures. According to history, Mr. Whittington and his wife really existed, lived a

luxurious and happy life in London, and had several children. Mr. Whittington was Sheriff, Major of London, and was later knighted by Henry V.

Conclusion

In Uzbek fairy tales, such as Darius, Iskandar Zulqarnayn, Alisher Navoi, Husayn Boykara, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, real anthroponyms such as King Arthur, King Edward III, King Henry V, Sir Whittington can be found in English fairy tales. This means that the names of kings, kings, and people with high status and prestige are often used in fairy tales.

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